

Flux-profile characterization of the offshore ABL for the parameterization of CFD models

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Abstract

The vertical structure of the stable atmospheric boundary layer (ABL) in open-sea offshore conditions is characterized based on flux-profile measurements at the Fino1 met mast, 45 km off the coast of Germany, during the first six months of 2006. The large data availability of flux measurements at three height levels (40, 60 and 80 m) allow a careful selection of profiles for which the most important ABL parameters of CFDWind model are obtained in non-dimensional form: velocity gradient, mixing-length, turbulent kinetic energy and eddy viscosity.

Similar to onshore conditions, the non-dimensional ABL parameters show local scaling behaviour based on local Obukhov length and friction velocity scales. Functional relationships are extracted and compared to classical functions used over land. The non-dimensional wind shear is larger than the classical Dyer's function at moderate stabilities probably due to the presence of low-level jets. A weak dependency of the non-dimensional turbulent kinetic energy on stability is noticed at moderate to high stabilities. Using a calibrated stability function, it is possible to match the mean wind shear and mixing length profiles with CFDWind mixing-length model in the same way as it is done in onshore conditions. Nevertheless, the large spread of the flux-profile data reveals that ABL scaling might be not only dependent on local z/L but also on other parameters like the wave age.

Ensemble-averaged profiles are reasonably well reproduced with quasy-steady simulations allowing to extend traditional CFD-based wind resource assessment methodologies to account for stability without the need to run costly unstable simulations.

1. Introduction

In operational wind resource assessment it is standard practice to use numerical models based on Monin-Obukhov similarity theory for the surface boundary layer. Such approach is justified in onshore wind energy sites, with the argument that these sites are normally subjected to high winds, where neutral atmospheric conditions dominate.

Using surface boundary layer models for offshore wind resource assessment produces unsatisfactory results in stable atmospheric conditions [1]. A very shallow stable boundary layer develops, due to the very low roughness of the sea surface, producing low-level jets of high wind shear. The increasing size of modern wind turbines further contributes to extend the area of interest beyond the surface layer, regardless of the terrain or wind conditions. To this end full-ABL models are required which account for the turbulent structure up to the geostrophic wind.

This paper presents a flux-profile analysis based on six months of data from the Fino1 offshore met mast. Local scaling of the stable ABL will be verified in offshore conditions comparing with classical functional forms obtained in onshore conditions. The flux-profile relationships will be used to calibrate CFDWind mixing-length model in order to validate it for the relevant range of stabilities observed in Fino1.

2. CFDWind ABL model

The offshore open-sea environment is a very appealing test bench for ABL models since there are no modifications of the flow because of elevation and roughness changes as it is typically the case in onshore conditions. In this sense the flow at microscale level can be considered horizontally homogeneous since

there are only dependencies of the flow variables with the height above the water level.

Under horizontally-homogeneous conditions, the Reynolds averaged equations for the horizontal velocity components (U, V) and potential temperature Θ for the dry ABL, with no radiation and phase-change heat transfer, read:

$$\begin{aligned}\frac{\partial U}{\partial t} &= f_c(V - V_g) - \frac{\partial \langle uw \rangle}{\partial z} \\ \frac{\partial V}{\partial t} &= -f_c(U - U_g) - \frac{\partial \langle vw \rangle}{\partial z} \\ \frac{\partial \Theta}{\partial t} &= -\frac{\partial \langle w\theta \rangle}{\partial z}\end{aligned}\quad (1)$$

where U_g and V_g are the horizontal components of the geostrophic wind, and $f_c = 2\Omega \sin\varphi$, the Coriolis parameter (Ω is the Earth's rotational speed and φ is the latitude).

The kinematic shear stress components $\langle uw \rangle$ and $\langle vw \rangle$ and kinematic heat flux $\langle w\theta \rangle$, where $\{u, v, w, \theta\}$ are velocity and potential temperature perturbations about the mean values, are modeled through eddy-diffusivity coefficients that relate the turbulent fluxes with the mean velocity and potential temperature gradients:

$$\langle uw \rangle, \langle vw \rangle = -K_m \left(\frac{\partial U}{\partial z}, \frac{\partial V}{\partial z} \right) \quad (2)$$

$$\langle w\theta \rangle = -\frac{K_m}{\sigma_t} \frac{\partial \Theta}{\partial z} \quad (3)$$

$\sigma_t = 1$ is the turbulent Prandtl number. The turbulent viscosity closes the set of equations and is related to the turbulent kinetic energy k (*tke*) and the mixing length l_m by:

$$K_m = l_m (\alpha k)^{1/2} \quad (4)$$

where:

$$\alpha = C_\mu^{1/2} = \frac{u_*^2}{k} \quad (5)$$

a constant that can be obtained from flux measurements and typically takes values like 0.09 or 0.033.

A transport equation for the turbulent kinetic energy k is solved:

$$\frac{\partial k}{\partial t} = G - \varepsilon + \frac{\partial}{\partial z} \left(\frac{K_m}{\sigma_k} \frac{\partial k}{\partial z} \right) \quad (6)$$

where $\sigma_k = 1$, G represents the production of *tke* due to shear and thermal stratification and ε is the turbulent dissipation rate which is related to the mixing length:

$$l_m = \frac{(\alpha k)^{3/2}}{\varepsilon} \quad (7)$$

so that the turbulent viscosity can be expressed as:

$$K_m = \alpha^2 \frac{k^2}{\varepsilon} \quad (8)$$

The turbulence closure described so far is of 1.5 order. Other higher-order closures exist but they will not be considered herein for sake of simplicity.

The mixing length is introduced as a diagnostic equation following [2]:

$$l_m = \frac{\kappa z}{\phi_m(z/L) + \frac{\kappa z}{\lambda}} \quad (9)$$

where $\phi_m(z/L)$ is the non-dimensional wind shear that depends on the stability parameter z/L , with L being the local Obukhov length:

$$L = -\frac{u_*^3}{\kappa \frac{g}{\theta_0} \overline{w\theta}} \quad (9)$$

where $\kappa = 0.4$ is the von Karman constant, g the acceleration due to gravity, θ_0 is a reference temperature and u_* the local friction velocity. By using local fluxes we adopt local scaling theory [3], which is a generalization to the full ABL of the Monin-Obukhov theory for the surface layer in stable conditions. λ is a limiting mixing length in neutral conditions that can be parameterized using the Blackadar expression [4]:

$$\lambda = 2.7 \cdot 10^{-4} \frac{S_g}{|f_c|}; \quad \lambda = 6.3 \cdot 10^{-3} \frac{u_*}{|f_c|} \quad (10)$$

where S_g is the modulus of the geostrophic wind. The non-dimensional wind shear in stable conditions ϕ_m is obtained from flux-gradient analysis as it will be shown later. Typical expressions from Dyer [5]:

$$\phi_m(z/L) = 1 + 5 \frac{z}{L} \quad (11)$$

and Duynkerke [6]:

$$\phi_m(z/L) = 1 + b_m \left(1 + \frac{b_m z}{a_m L} \right)^{a_m - 1} \quad (12)$$

with constants $a_m=0.8$ $b_m=5$, can be found in the literature.

The ABL model is forced with the geostrophic wind in the top boundary, with zero gradient of tk_e . In the bottom boundary, the friction velocity is dynamically computed together with the roughness length for offshore conditions, following Charnock's relation [7]:

$$z_0 = C_{ch} \frac{u_*^2}{g} \quad (13)$$

with a value $C_{ch}=0.0062$ obtained from Fino1 velocity profiles in neutral conditions. This value falls within the range observed in the literature [8]. Charnock's function accounts for the growing wave height with higher wind shear stress.

The CFDWind mixing-length model described so far is calibrated with the following functions and constants:

- The dimensionless wind shear $\phi(z/L)$
- The dimensionless $tk_e = C\mu$, which can eventually depend on z/L
- The Charnock constant C_{ch}
- The limiting mixing length in neutral conditions λ

3. The Fino1 dataset

The FINO-1 offshore platform is located 45km off the Borknun Island in Germany (54.014°N, 6.5905°E). A 100-m mast fully equipped with meteorological and oceanographic instruments is measuring since 2003. Profile measurements of velocity at 8 levels (33, 40, 50, 60, 70, 80, 90 and 100m) temperature and relative humidity at 5 levels (33, 40, 50, 70 and 100m) are averaged at 10min intervals. Three sonic anemometers located at 40, 60 and 80m measure at 10Hz the 3D velocity components. Sonic anemometer measurements are available for the year 2006 although the 60m sensor only works during the first half of the year, which is the evaluation period selected in this study.

Atmospheric stratification dominates de offshore ABL at Fino1 in the wind turbine operational range (Figure 1). Atmospheric

stability is driven by differences of temperature between the sea surface and the air aloft.

Figure 1: Distribution of velocity (black line) and stability at 40m level (N=neutral $|L|>1000m$, SU=slightly unstable $-1000m < L < -200m$, VU=very unstable $-200m < L < 0$, SS=slightly stable $200m < L < 1000m$, VS=very stable $0 < L < 200m$)

Only open water conditions are considered, without mast distortion effects, reducing the analysis to the wind direction sector $225^\circ \pm 45^\circ$.

Sonic anemometer measurements are rotated to the mean streamline coordinate system using the planar fit method [9][10]. Since the mean streamline plane has to be parallel to the sea surface, it is possible to infer mounted tilt angles and correct for them. Tilt angles from 1 to 1.8° are found in the three sonics during the evaluation period. Variances and covariances of detrended velocity and sonic temperature perturbations are computed using the eddy-correlation technique over a 5min timescale. Then, turbulent fluxes are obtained by averaging the covariances over a period of 1 hr. Profile data is also averaged to 1hr intervals so as to obtain a synchronized dataset. One hour intervals are required in order to reduce random flux errors and avoid excessive scatter in the flux-profile analysis.

Before the flux-profile analysis, quality control of the data is performed in order to remove spurious or low-quality data.

4. Flux-Profile Analysis

The analysis of non-dimensional parameters in stable conditions requires significant filtering on the dataset in order to avoid excessive scatter.

Much of the scatter can be eliminated by removing data with very low turbulence and near zero fluxes and gradients. Small flux data are characterized by larger measurement errors and may be more modulated by mesoscale trends [11]. Hence, minimum thresholds in the kinematic heat flux (0.0001 mKs^{-1}) and the velocity gradient (0.01 s^{-1}) are set at the three sonic levels. An impression of the impact of these last filters is shown in the figures with grey markers. As a result of all the filtering a total of 609 hourly profiles are retained in the dataset.

Velocity gradients are obtained by curve fitting of the cup anemometer velocity profiles (8 levels) to a log-linear function:

$$U = P_1 z + P_2 \ln z + P_3 \quad (14)$$

$$\frac{\partial U}{\partial z} = P_1 + \frac{P_2}{z} \quad (15)$$

where P_i are the regression coefficients obtained by least-squares fit. Then, the non-dimensional wind shear (Figure 2) is calculated as:

$$\phi_m(z/L) = \frac{\kappa z}{u_*} \frac{\partial U}{\partial z} \quad (16)$$

with the friction velocity obtained from the kinematic momentum fluxes:

$$u_* = \left(\overline{uW}^2 + \overline{vW}^2 \right)^{1/4} \quad (17)$$

The validity of local scaling is demonstrated as the three measurement levels collapse into a single trend, which depends on the local stability parameter z/L . Functional forms (11) and (12), obtained in onshore conditions, are also shown. It is observed that the velocity gradient is underestimated by these functions in the range of moderate stabilities ($0.02 < L < 2$) where most of the data is found. A better fit of (12) to the Fino1 data is obtained with $b_m=12$.

The higher wind shear observed in the stable marine boundary layer is explained in [12] by the presence of low-level jets that produce a maximum in the velocity profile at low heights, of the order of 100-200m, and larger shear than would be otherwise expected.

Figure 2: Non-dimensional velocity shear ϕ_m dependence on local stability parameter z/L

The turbulent kinetic energy is defined as half the sum of the mean-square fluctuations:

$$TKE \equiv E = \frac{1}{2} (\overline{u^2} + \overline{v^2} + \overline{w^2}) \quad (18)$$

The dimensionless form is obtained by dividing by the local shear stress $\tau = u_*^2$ (Figure 3). Monin-Obukhov theory provides a functional expression based on the dimensionless velocity and turbulent dissipation rate ϕ_ϵ shear.

$$\frac{tke}{u_*^2}(z/L) = \frac{1}{\sqrt{C_\mu}} \left(\frac{\phi_m(z/L)}{\phi_\epsilon(z/L)} \right)^2 \quad (18)$$

where [6]:

$$\phi_\epsilon(z/L) = \phi_m(z/L) + z/L \quad (19)$$

assuming that production of tke equals dissipation.

Figure 3 shows the non-dimensional tke dependency on stability. Even though the three observational levels show the same trend, this one has a different behavior than the one expected from onshore functional forms in the range of moderate stabilities. Besides, the scatter is very significant. These results suggest that the scaling of turbulence in the offshore ABL cannot be defined by a function of the local stability parameter only. The appearance of a minimum around $z/L=0.5$ could be evidence of the influence of the wave age, i.e. the ratio of the phase velocity of the wave and the surface friction velocity [13][14], which determines the structure of the lower levels of the marine ABL.

In the low stability range ($0 < L < 0.1$) the non-dimensional tke is independent of stability and takes the constant value of neutral conditions ($C_\mu^{-0.5}$).

Figure 3: Non-dimensional turbulent kinetic energy dependence on local stability parameter z/L

The eddy viscosity is calculated based on the momentum flux and velocity gradient:

$$K_m = -\frac{\overline{wU}}{\partial U / \partial z} \quad (20)$$

whose non-dimensional form is obtained by dividing by the product of the scaling velocity and length scales.

Figure 4: Non-dimensional eddy viscosity dependence on local stability parameter z/L

The three levels collapse into the same trend and show a leveling off at $z/L > 1$, so called z-less regime [3], where turbulence does not depend anymore on the distance above the ground. This is less clearly observed in the wind

shear and tke plots. This z-less regime is characteristic of the free atmosphere [15] indicating that in many very stable situations the 80m level at Fino1 lays in the upper part of the boundary layer.

Figure 5: Non-dimensional mixing length dependence on local stability parameter z/L

The mixing length is an important turbulence scale in first-order turbulent closures. It is defined as:

$$l_m = \frac{u_*}{\partial U / \partial z} \quad (21)$$

Expression (9) suggests that the mixing length is limited by the height from the surface close to the ground ($l_m \sim kz$), then by the Coriolis asymptotic length λ at intermediate heights and by the local Obukhov length L in the ABL top. The dependency on stability is provided by the stability function ϕ_m . Figure 5 shows the ratio of the mixing length and the surface layer mixing-length kz . Neutral turbulence scales of the order of 30m are significantly reduced by increasing stabilities down to sizes of the order of 1m or less in the upper part of the boundary layer.

Dyer's stability function (11) tends to overestimate the mixing length at all stabilities. The calibrated function is more appropriate for the parameterization of the mixing length.

The flux-gradient and turbulence plots are all affected by self-correlation, which happens when one or more variables appears in the functions represented in both axes of the scatter plot. Unfortunately the level of self correlation is not straightforward to evaluate. Although the scatter is severely affected by self-correlation in ϕ_m , the slope of the curve is

not that sensitive [16]. The same could be expected for the other parameters.

5. Validation of CFDWind

CFDWind was validated in onshore neutral conditions in [17] using the Leipzig wind profile. The mixing length model presented here for the stable ABL was verified with the GABLS test case [18] and was validated in the Antarctic stable ABL [19].

The GABLS test case [18] is based on a boundary layer driven by a prescribed uniform geostrophic in the top and a constant cooling rate in the bottom surface. The simulation is run for nine hours from prescribed initial conditions until quasi-steady state is reached. The same procedure is followed here in order to produce quasi-steady profiles for different stability classes:

- Near-neutral: $0 < z/L < 0.01$
- Moderately stable: $0.1 < z/L < 0.2$
- Highly stable: $1 < z/L < 2$

The 40m level is taken as the reference for the near-surface Obukhov length and friction velocity. Ensemble averaged profiles are obtained for each class and compared with the simulated quasi-steady profiles after 9hr with CFDWind. Table 1 shows the characteristics of the ensemble averaged profiles.

Table 1: Ensemble averaged profile classes

Class	#	L_{40} [m]	u_{40}^* [ms^{-1}]	U_{40}/u_{40}^*
Neutral	7	8000	0.518	31.09
Mod. Stable	169	274	0.318	37.24
Very Stable	16	31	0.123	72.12

Since the geostrophic wind is not known from the measurements, the simulated profiles are obtained by iteration until the output profiles match the z/L and U/u_* values at 40m.

Figure 6 to 8 show the profiles of the dimensionless velocity, shear stress and tke for the three stability conditions of Table 1 from: ensemble averages of the observations (the error bars indicate the variability of the ensemble based on one standard deviation at both sides of the mean value) and CFDWind simulations using Dyer's stability function (11) or the best fit of (12). Besides, the Monin-Obukhov log-law for the velocity in the surface

layer is also presented as a reference. This law is obtained by integrating (16) using Dyer's stability function:

$$U = \frac{u_{*0}}{\kappa} \left(\ln \frac{z}{z_0} + 5 \frac{z}{L_0} \right) \quad (22)$$

where the surface layer friction velocity u_{*0} and Obukhov length L_0 are referred to the 40m level.

Figure 6: Ensemble-averaged profiles, Monin-Obukhov surface layer log-law and CFDWind simulations for near-neutral case ($0 < z/L_{40} < 0.01$)

The neutral case shows that the shear stress is roughly constant between 40 and 60m, indicating surface layer conditions. Using the mean friction velocity of these two levels and M-O log-law it was derived the value of the Charnock constant (13). Both CFDWind simulations fall in the same line since both assume $\phi_m=1$ in neutral conditions.

The boundary layer height, considered as the level at which the tke falls to 5% of the surface value in the CFDWind simulations, is located at 1183m. The surface layer height, defined as the level at which the shear stress falls to 90% of the surface value is 100m. Hence, in this case all the mast is immersed in the surface layer and M-O remains valid.

The moderately stable case shows much more variability in the ensemble than in neutral conditions. Nevertheless, it is observed that the ensemble mean is well reproduced by quasi-steady simulations of CFDWind when the calibrated stability function is used. Using

classical Dyer's formulation still produces a good velocity and shear stress profiles but leads to higher tke . The M-O theory is not valid since the surface layer is already below the 40m level. Indeed, the boundary layer height based on the calibrated model is at 291m and the surface layer at 39m.

Figure 7: Ensemble-averaged profiles, Monin-Obukhov surface layer log-law and CFDWind simulations for moderately stable case ($0.1 < z/L_{40} < 0.2$)

Figure 8: Ensemble-averaged profiles, Monin-Obukhov surface layer log-law and CFDWind simulations for very stable case ($1 < z/L_{40} < 2$)

The ensemble of profiles in the very stable case show an even larger variability in the shear stress and tke due to very low values of the turbulent fluxes with result in much higher uncertainties. CFDWind simulations show a low-level jet around the 100m level which is

lower with Dyer's formulation than with the best fit function.

Again, the calibrated model agrees better with the ensemble mean velocity profile. In very stable conditions the ABL is characterized by very low turbulence with high intermittency and with the presence of gravity waves. These waves can add momentum in the upper part of the boundary layer increasing the shear stress as it is observed in the measurements. This unsteady phenomena cannot be reproduced by the CFDWind model. Nevertheless, the velocity profile can be predicted quite well. In this case, the boundary layer height is at 105m and the surface layer height at 13.5m.

6. Summary and Conclusions

Flux-profile analysis based on three levels of sonic anemometers has been presented. As in onshore conditions, the structure of the offshore stable ABL at Fino1 is characterized by local scaling with non-dimensional variables depending on the stability parameter z/L . In the other hand, classical functional forms of the dimensionless velocity shear and turbulent kinetic energy in onshore conditions do not fit the experimental data accurately, indicating the possible influence of other marine-related scaling parameters like the wave age.

CFDWind mixing-length model, validated in onshore conditions, has been tested in the offshore stable ABL. Ensemble averaged profiles at three different stability classes have been compared with quasi-steady profiles obtained following the GABLS procedure.

A recalibration of the dimensionless wind shear function has been introduced in order to improve the performance of CFDWind in Fino1. Even though some improvement is observed, the use of classical onshore stability functions also works reasonably well. Hence, for sake of universality, it is recommended to use classical functions in other sites unless site-specific calibration can be performed.

In general, it is observed that the quasi-steady simulations of the stable ABL can be used to characterize ensemble averaged profiles. This result allows us to use these quasi-steady simulations as input profiles for 3D CFD steady-

state models in the same way as it is done in neutral conditions, without the need of running costly unsteady 3D simulations. Then, CFD-based wind resource assessment methodologies can incorporate atmospheric stability for a more accurate classification of the wind climate. Of course, in order to extract the statistical distribution of stability on the site it is necessary to measure z/L at various heights using sonic anemometers. These instruments also allow a site-specific calibration of the turbulent structure of the ABL which will further improve the performance of the CFD model.

7. Acknowledgements

This work has been carried out with funding of the national project INNPACTO-EMERGE.

8. References

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